

**Continuing the article on the unit of spatial value S
and the unit of energy c^2**

The energy unit c^2 continuously creates the spatial value unit S (energy moving generates spatial value). When the energy unit is in free motion, it continuously creates space $c^2 \text{ km}^2$ (approximately 300.000^2 km^2) meaning S is completely transformed into space, as in the case of light, in which case its time is always zero. If the energy unit is stationary (a stationary system, the case of combining multiple energy units into mass), then S is simply 1 s^2 . When the energy unit is in motion, this part of S gradually transforms into space (the creation of space, not apparent space).

In Minkowski's formula, people always ask why the quantity S^2 (S^2 in Minkowski's formula, not S , the unit of spatial value) is always constant, as well as why $(ct)^2$ and $x^2 y^2 z^2$ have different signs. The difference in sign shows that time and space are essentially one, and here it's just a matter of compensation. For example, if $1 = 1$, then $1 - 1 = 0$. Similarly, S^2 is a constant quantity.

Because Minkowski's formula describes apparent space, we don't clearly see the meaning of S^2 or the use of apparent coordinates $x^2 y^2 z^2$. Instead, here it's just a conversion problem showing that the moving system has used spatial values to create space through its motion, so the difference with the stationary system is the remaining spatial value of the moving system and therefore, naturally, it remains constant regardless of which stationary system we compare it to (choosing different spacetime reference points).

We have: $S^2 = c^2t^2 - s^2$

From this, we can easily see that S^2 has causal significance, if $S^2 > 0$, there is a causal relationship because the system's motion does not exceed the speed of light. When $S^2 = 0$ the system is moving at the speed of light. When $S^2 < 0$ this is no longer a description consistent with the physical nature, but simply a mathematical operation between two events that cannot describe the movement of energy (exceeding c^2).

Thus, the true nature of reality, spacetime, is not a background field (there is no curvature of spacetime). Space is time and vice versa. This is the transformation of the unit of spatial value S as energy moves. The unit of energy is like a money bag that always generates S ; if the unit of energy moves, it uses this money to exchange for space, and the remaining money is time with an equivalent conversion: $1 S = 1 s^2 = 1 c^2 \text{ km}^2$ (c^2 approximately 300.000^2).

This is only a personal viewpoint that I would like to share from my own reflections. Thank you for reading these lines.